

TOUCH SENSATIONS IN AN ONLINE STORE. THE INFLUENCE OF IMAGE INTERACTIVITY ON EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE AND PRODUCT EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

In this study we build upon the persuasiveness of touch in product evaluations and extend it to an online store environment. We explore the contribution of image interactivity in mediated product experiences to perceived diagnosticity (i.e. the extent to which the shopping experience is deemed as helpful to evaluate the product), and emotional experience. Results of an experimental study (n=67) reveal that, compared to a static interface, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures led to higher levels of perceived diagnosticity and more favorable emotional responses. Additionally, little differences were observed between an interactive interface and actual touch. We also explore the moderating role of an individual's need for touch and conclude that an interactive interface is especially effective for consumers high in need of touch.

KEYWORDS: *touch; product experience; emotional responses; mediated environment; consumers*

INTRODUCTION

People tend to find personal experiences extremely compelling. Hoch (2002, p.448) even states that consumers are 'too trusting of what they have learned through experience'. This is one of the reasons why consumers' *direct* experience with a product, in which they continuously receive information through various senses, has proven to be highly persuasive (Smith, 1993). Obviously, sensory aspects of a product such as smell, touch, looks, sound and taste strongly influence product evaluations (Balaji et al., 2011; Krishna et al., n.d.). Together with vision, the tactile sense in particular is recognized as an important sensor to pass on acceptance (Sheldon & Arens, 1932). Our sense of touch 'provides us with information about the world, about the shape and weight of things, about its texture and temperature, its verticality and stability, and many other physical properties' (Hekkert, 2006, p.162). Touch can at times even directly compete with visual input. For example, Balaji and colleagues (2011) have shown that touch rather than vision is a preferred sensory modality for acquiring relevant information for products with important material properties, such as texture, hardness, and temperature. In a similar vein, recent research supports the idea that touch

is highly effective in influencing decision making, resulting in favorable consumer responses (Grohmann et al., 2007; McCabe & Nowlis, 2003). Touch can thus be used as a powerful product communication tool. Traditional brick-and-mortar stores are able to excite consumers through all their senses. However, online stores are limited in the sensory information they can offer. People can, for example, not physically handle products. This lack of direct experiential information is one of the main reasons why consumers remain hesitant to buy their products online (Citrin et al., 2003). As such, online retailers are challenged to integrate features in the online store to let consumers experience products 'as if they are real'. Hence, it is worthwhile looking for a substitute for touch since its underlying mechanisms could provide similar effects, in a mediated way, as actual touch. Remarkably, little is known about the role of (or the lack of) touch in product judgments and decision making in an online environment and how online retailers can overcome, or at least decrease, this barrier by providing mediated touch.

Building further upon the persuasiveness of touch, the primary objective of this study is to demonstrate that an interface with *image interactivity* to simulate stroking gestures can tap into tactile perceptual information and in this way affect product

understanding and emotional responses. Furthermore, it is expected that the effect of image interactivity on emotional responses is more apparent for people who have a chronic preference for hedonic aspects of touch, such as seeking fun, arousal, and excitement.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Interdependence between touch and vision

Information gathered through vision and touch partly overlaps. Therefore, vision is considered to offer an alternative exploratory option that could be used in conjunction with, or instead of, tactile exploration (Yazdanparast & Spears, 2012). For example, the steam rising from a cup of tea tells us something about the temperature of that cup. Further, Klatzky et al. (1991) suggest that, when deprived of 'actual' touch, mental tactile exploration during visual imagery provides access to information about tactually accessible object attributes (e.g., roughness of a tennis ball). In the same way, Anema and colleagues (2012) demonstrated that visual stimuli are able to guide thinking about touch elements, which subsequently facilitates tactile sensations. More specifically, participants reported they could vividly feel the sensation to the skin when visualizing grasping a hand full of the gravel depicted in a picture, despite the fact that there was no actual tactile stimulus present. In fact, studies in the field of neuroscience have revealed considerable overlap between tactile imagery and neural mechanisms underlying real tactile perception, insofar as it activates at least some of the same brain areas (Keysers et al., 2004; Spence & Gallace, 2011). Hence, sensory input in one modality is capable of eliciting an experience in a different sensory modality. However, research on visual input and feelings of touch is mostly limited to static images. The role of image interactivity in inducing mediated touch sensations remains relatively unexplored, despite recent important technological advances.

Image interactivity & perceived diagnosticity

If actual touch affects product judgments and decision making, could an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures have a similar effect? The present study adopts *image interactivity* in a mediated environment as a way to induce some of the stimulation consumers normally derive from product touch. Steuer (1992, p.84) defines interactivity as 'the extent to which users can participate in modifying the form or content of a mediated environment in real time'. Image interactivity allows the user to directly manipulate objects in a virtual environment. As a result, there is a continuous change in graphics that bear a close resemblance to physical actions — as if events are occurring in the physical world (Schlosser, 2003). Most online stores currently employ a basic form of image interactivity technology (e.g., a static image with an extensive zoom). However, advanced image interactivity allows users to manipulate and modify the form of an object more

directly; an example of an advanced image interactivity interface is the Shoogle¹, see Figure 1. The interactive interface allows users to 'move' fabric by dragging their mouse, hence simulating stroking gestures. Such a new digitally interactive way to represent objects has been proposed to be able to bring the digital experience of products closer to reality (Wu et al., 2011). In this paper we set out to investigate whether it can provide consumers with similar kinds of information normally available through direct experiential contact with the product (e.g., fabric flexibility or softness).

Fig. 1. Example of the image interactivity interface

Continuing with the above reasoning, a product experience is deemed as helpful and relevant when the experience serves an informational function for consumers considering a purchase (Kempf & Smith, 1998; Lee et al., 2012). That's exactly what perceived diagnosticity is about. Perceived diagnosticity is conceptualized as 'the perceived ability of the shopping experience to provide relevant product information to help consumers accurately evaluate product attributes' (Lee et al., 2012, p.382). Some product attributes (e.g., texture, softness, flexibility) can be evaluated only by using the product directly, also known as *experience attributes* (Nelson, 1974). Critical to the value of this experience is the perceived diagnosticity of information gathered through touch in helping to make informed product decisions. Interfaces generating high levels of image interactivity allow users to manipulate a product in an online environment. The interactive cues may generate a

1 Surf for an interactive example to http://www.shoogleit.com/2622-o_NOORA-sjaal

vivid, informative, and impressive presentation of the product. We hypothesize that an interactive interface will be perceived as diagnostic when evaluating experience attributes because image interactivity conveys tactile information on these attributes, while a static interface does not. Furthermore, an interactive interface may sufficiently capture experience attributes in such a way that touching the actual product doesn't provide more information.

H1: An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures significantly increases perceived diagnosticity of experience attributes, compared to a regular interface with only static images.

Emotional responses

Thus far, we have focused on the informational function of touch. However, studies have also found an immediate, automatic emotional response toward the touched object (Peck & Shu, 2009; Peck & Wiggins, 2006). Emotions can be elicited through a stimulation of our senses by product appearance (Isbister et al., 2007). Tactile input in particular is linked to affect and plays an important role in how consumers perceive products (Jansson-Boyd, 2011). More specifically, by altering the tactile surfaces, it has been proposed that it is possible to make consumers feel connected to a product on an emotional level (Jansson-Boyd, 2011; Sonneveld & Schifferstein, 2008). For example, an empirical study (Essick et al., 1999) has shown that soft and smooth fabric materials were consistently perceived as more pleasant to touch than those that were stiff, rough or coarse. Touching a pleasantly valenced object can result in positive emotional responses toward the object even if touch elements provide no information regarding the product (Peck & Shu, 2009). These hedonic aspects of touch thus seem to appear independent of the informational function of touch. Therefore, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures is expected to compensate for a lack of touch, and in this way may serve as a substitute for touch in order to enjoy the hedonic aspect of product experiences.

H2: An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures results in more positive emotional responses during product evaluation compared to a regular interface with only static images.

Additionally, emotions play a role when consumers are prevented from touching products, as is the case in online environments, affecting the judgment decisions that they make (Jansson-Boyd, 2011). If consumers feel the need to touch products and are not allowed to do so, it can lead to a strong sense of dissatisfaction, a negative emotional response, making them avoid mediated shopping environments (Citrin et al., 2003; McCabe & Nowlis, 2003). Hence, we hypothesize that different from a static interface, an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures is able to reduce negative feelings, because the interactive cues emphasize tactile information.

H3: An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures results in less negative emotions during product evaluation compared to a regular interface with

only static images.

Need for touch

Individuals differ in their predilection for tactile information; hence the effects of touch differ across people. Peck and Childers (2003a, p.431) identify individual differences in need for touch (NFT), that is, 'a person's preference for the extraction and utilization of information obtained through touch'. Furthermore, NFT is conceptualized as having two dimensions: instrumental NFT and autotelic NFT (Peck & Childers, 2003a). In this study we focus on the autotelic dimension of NFT. Individuals who are high in autotelic NFT engage in touch because it is fun, an experience that is far more hedonic than instrumental. An individual who is high in autotelic NFT often feels an irresistible need to engage in exploratory touch and is focused on the sensory aspects of touch as an end in itself (Peck & Wiggins, 2006). An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures is expected to compensate for a lack of touch primarily for high autotelic haptically motivated consumers. Such an interactive interface would be expected to satisfy people who have a chronic preference for hedonic aspects of touch such as seeking fun, arousal, and excitement. In the same way, when this specific group of consumers is deprived of tactile stimulation (only static images are present) they can feel strong negative emotions precisely because an enjoyable substitute for touch is lacking. However, individuals who are low in autotelic NFT do not find touch as inherently interesting or as irresistible. Consequently, compensation for a lack of touch is not as important for consumers who are low in autotelic NFT.

H4: Compared to a regular interface with only static images, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures will (a) increase positive emotions (b) decrease negative emotions for people who are high in autotelic NFT, but will not affect emotional responses for those who are low in autotelic NFT.

METHOD

Participants and design

Only female participants were selected to eliminate gender-specific preference for the product since it was a feminine item. Accordingly, 67 female undergraduates participated in a twenty-minute experiment conducted in a controlled laboratory environment. All participants received a participation fee of five euros. A quasi-experiment, consisting of a 3 (mediated touch: static interface, mediated touch: interactive interface, actual touch) X 2 (low vs. high NFT) between-subjects design was employed wherein NFT reflects a person's chronic preference to touch. Inclusion of an 'actual touch condition' as a control condition enables us to compare the effects of image interactivity with the effects of actually handling the product.

Stimuli

Experimental product. A scarf was used as the experimental product. Research has consistently shown that clothing is clearly a product category for which tactile input is diagnostic in the evaluation processes (Grohmann et al., 2007; Jansson-Boyd, 2011). A pretest among 56 female students ($M_{\text{age}}=22.29$) was conducted to verify if scarfs would be an appropriate product category. The first objective was to test if tactile input is diagnostic for scarfs. A 7-point Likert scale measured mode of product evaluation (e.g. 'It is difficult to judge the quality of a scarf through visual inspection alone', based on a scale applied in Smith & Park, 1992). The average score was significantly higher than the neutral point (i.e., $H_0: M_x = 4$; $M_{\text{mode}}=4.84$, $t_{(55)}=4.87$, $p<.001$), which implies that participants indicated that various attributes of a scarf must be assessed through actual trial and not through visual inspection alone. The second objective of the pretest was to determine the salient attributes to evaluate a scarf. Through a free elicitation assignment, participants were asked to list product attributes that they thought were important to consider for the selection of a scarf. The pretest results showed that material, warmth, softness, and thickness of the scarf could be identified as experience attributes most important to product choice.

Product presentation manipulation. We manipulated the product presentation by creating two mediated product experiences as experimental conditions. Two webpages of a fictitious online store were designed. In the 'mediated touch: static interface' condition (www.static.uasurvey.be), the product was displayed on a webpage accompanying the scarfs' picture and a picture of some details of the scarf. The webpage also included an extensive zoom option similar to webpages of currently available online stores. In the 'mediated touch: interactive interface' condition (www.uasurvey.be), the scarf was displayed on a webpage in the same way as in the static interface condition, the only difference being that users were allowed to modify the form of the product by using the Shoogle. As control condition we created an actual product experience, wherein participants were able to physically examine the actual scarf. To provide all participants with identical written product information, a product label containing a written description similar to the description on the webpage was attached to the scarf.

Procedure

Participants were invited to visit a lab individually and sat at a table in front of a computer monitor. Potential intervening variables such as browser type (chrome 31.0.1650.63 m), Internet connection speed, and instructions were kept constant. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the three conditions. To be sure all participants were sufficiently involved in the evaluation task, participants could choose to take part in a price drawing (instructions can be found in appendix A). In this way, a relevant product evaluation situation was created (i.e., participants had to consider if they found the scarf worthy/valuable enough to participate in the price drawing). Subsequently, participants either saw the product presented on a

webpage or had the opportunity to actually touch the product (the participants were instructed to take the scarf out of the drawer, so touch was assured). After a 1 ½ minute product examination, participants filled out measures relating to the dependent variables of the study. After completing the questionnaire, participants were debriefed and thanked.

Measures

All of the following measures were adapted from pre-validated measures in consumer behavior studies. Below is a brief description, more details for all measures can be found in Appendix B.

Manipulation checks. To verify whether the manipulation of involvement was successful, participants were asked to fill in a scale based on Pham, 1996 ($\alpha=.80$). Subsequently, to assess the level of perceived feelings of touch for participants in the mediated conditions, a measure developed by Peck and colleagues (2013) was used ($\alpha=.82$).

Perceived diagnosticity. In this study, perceived diagnosticity was measured at the attribute rather than product level. We measured perceived diagnosticity across the scarf's salient experience attributes: material, warmth, thickness, and softness. The four items were averaged for a measure of perceived diagnosticity ($\alpha=.81$).

Emotional responses. Emotional responses were measured using the visual self-report instrument PrEmo (Desmet, 2003), containing six positive and six negative emotions. We averaged the positive emotions for a measure of positive responses ($\alpha=.82$), and did the same for a measure of negative responses ($\alpha=.75$).

Need for touch. Participants had to complete the autotelic component of the NFT scale ($\alpha=.89$) developed by Peck and Childers (2003a).

RESULTS

Manipulation checks

Involvement. A one sample t-test revealed that the average score on involvement was significantly higher than the neutral point (i.e., $H_0: M_x=4$; $M_{\text{inv}}=5.32$, $t_{(66)}=11.69$, $p<.01$), suggesting that participants were sufficiently involved in evaluating the product thoroughly. Results of an ANOVA revealed no significant differences between the three conditions with regard to the level of involvement ($F_{(2,64)}=0.77$, NS).

Perceived feeling of touch. A t-test was run and a significant effect of product presentation on perceived feelings of touch was found ($t_{(42)}=-4.64$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.34$). As expected, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures resulted in significantly greater perceived feelings of touch than a static interface (see figure 2), implying that participants in the interactive condition reported more frequently that they actually had the feeling of the scarf in their hands.

Fig. 2. Mean perceived feelings of touch by product presentation.

Perceived diagnosticity

H1 predicted that participants would find an interactive interface more diagnostic for experience attributes during product evaluation than a static interface. As expected, the effect of product presentation on perceived diagnosticity of experience attributes was highly significant ($F_{(2,64)}=13.72, p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.30$). Planned contrasts revealed that the mean score of participants after exposure to an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures was higher ($M=4.90$) than the mean score of participants after exposure to a regular interface with only static images ($M=3.89; t_{(64)}=3.45, p<.01, r=.40$). Subsequently, we observed no significant difference in perceived diagnosticity between the interactive interface condition and the condition where actual touch was possible ($M=5.38; t_{(64)}=1.66, NS$). The results indicate that participants who interact with an interface simulating stroking gestures perceived the product experience as highly diagnostic for product attributes such as thickness and softness, which was similar to participants who actually handled the product.

Positive emotional responses

H2 stated that simulating stroking gestures using image interactivity would result in more positive emotional responses. To test this proposition, an ANOVA was performed with an averaged measure of positive emotional response as the dependent variable, and product presentation as the independent variable. The results revealed a significant main effect for positive emotional responses ($F_{(2,63)}=4.14, p<.05, \eta^2=.12$). Overall, participants reported positive emotional responses when they could physically touch the product ($M=1.71$). When participants used an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures during product evaluation they reported even slightly more positive emotional responses ($M=1.95$). However, when tactile information was limited because the product was presented by means of a regular interface with only static images, positive emotional reactions dropped considerably ($M=1.29$). As expected, planned contrast tests revealed that an interactive interface elicited more positive emotional responses than a static interface ($t_{(63)}=2.84, p<.01, r=.34$). Positive emotional responses elicited by the interactive interface, again, did not differ from that of actual product interactions ($t_{(63)}=1.01, NS$). Subsequently, in order to establish whether responses differed over product presentation for each specific emotion, a MANOVA was performed with six positive emotional responses as dependent variables, and product presentation as an independent variable. Using Pillai's trace, there was a significant main effect for positive emotional responses ($V=0.62, F_{(12,118)}=4.45, p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.31$). Looking at the emotions individually using separate univariate ANOVAs, we learned that desire ($F_{(2,63)}=5.12, p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.14$), fascination ($F_{(2,63)}=5.01, p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.14$), and joy ($F_{(2,63)}=11.02, p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.26$) are important emotional responses to touch experiences. The emotions, satisfaction, pride, and hope are less relevant because the effect of product presentation on these three specific emotions failed to reach significance ($p>.12$). Planned contrast tests revealed that an interactive interface significantly ($M=1.64$) increased feelings of desire compared to a static

Fig. 3. Mean emotional responses for static and interactive condition

Fig. 4. Mean emotional responses for actual and interactive condition

interface ($M=.73$; $t_{(63)}=2.77$, $p<.01$, $r=.33$). Furthermore, an interactive interface can elicit feelings of desire in the same way as actual touch ($M=1.64$; $t_{63}=0.00$, NS), whereas a static interface almost entirely fails to elicit feelings of desire. The same pattern is true for joy (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). Likewise, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures elicits fascination to a greater extent than a static interface does ($t_{(63)}=2.97$, $p<.01$, $r=.37$). Interestingly, participants in the interactive condition are significantly more fascinated than participants in the actual condition ($t_{(63)}=2.43$, $p<.05$, $r=.29$).

Negative emotional responses

H3 predicted that an interactive interface is capable of suppressing negative emotional responses typically elicited by the absence of tactile information. To test this assumption an ANOVA was performed with an averaged measure of negative emotional responses as the dependent variable and product presentation as the independent variable. A significant main effect was found ($F_{(2,63)}=6.94$, $p<.01$, $\eta^2=.18$). As predicted, a regular interface with only static images elicited the most negative emotional responses ($M=0.71$). While both actual touch ($M=0.15$), and an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures ($M=0.34$), elicited less negative emotional responses. Planned contrast tests show that a static interface elicited significantly more negative emotional responses than the interactive interface ($t_{(32)}=2.07$, $p<.05$, $r=.25$), whereas participants who physically examined the product reported levels of negative emotional responses similar to participants who used the interactive interface ($t_{(35)}=1.88$, NS). These results support H3. To further inspect specific negative emotions a MANOVA was performed with six negative emotional responses as dependent variables and product presentation as independent variable. Overall, using Pillai's trace a significant main effect of product presentation on negative emotional responses was found ($V=0.38$, $F_{(12,118)}=2.33$, $p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.19$). Separate univariate ANOVAs reveal that disgust ($F_{(2,63)}=4.85$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.13$), dissatisfaction ($F_{(2,63)}=9.03$, $p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.22$), shame ($F_{(2,63)}=3.18$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.09$), fear ($F_{(2,63)}=3.35$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.10$), and boredom ($F_{(2,63)}=4.91$, $p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.14$) are important emotional drivers of negative responses elicited by product presentation. Planned contrast tests reveal that a static interface provoked far more feelings of dissatisfaction ($M=0.91$) than an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures ($M=0.23$; $t_{(32)}=2.79$, $p<.01$, $r=.44$). While the latter provoked similar low levels of dissatisfaction as actually handling the product ($M=0.09$; $t_{(33)}=1.06$, NS). In the same way, participants exposed to a static interface were clearly more bored ($M=1.59$) than participants exposed to an interactive interface ($M=0.59$; $t_{(63)}=2.89$, $p<.01$, $r=.34$). Whereas the difference in boredom between an interactive interface and actually handling the product ($M=0.97$) proved to be non-significant ($t_{(63)}=0.39$, NS). See Figures 3 and 4 for a graphic display of the results.

Moderating role of NFT

In this paragraph we focus on the moderating role of autotelic NFT in mediated product experiences. To distinguish

between participants high in autotelic NFT, compared to those low in autotelic NFT, the variable was dichotomized based on a median split ($Mdn=5.83$; $M_{highNFT}=6.37$, $M_{lowNFT}=4.93$; $t_{(65)}=-11.28$, $p<.001$). The moderating role of NFT on actual product experiences is already established in literature (Peck & Childers, 2003a, 2003b). Therefore, and for reasons of brevity, we decided not to include the actual touch condition in the following analyses.

H4a predicted that compared to a regular interface with only static images, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures would increase positive emotions for people who are in autotelic NFT, but will not result in more positive emotions for those who are low in autotelic NFT. However, the interaction effect between product presentation and autotelic NFT showed to be non-significant ($F_{(2,62)}=1.37$, NS), providing no support for autotelic NFT affecting positive emotional responses (H4a is rejected).

On the contrary, when examining the effect of autotelic NFT and product presentation on negative emotions, we detected a significant interaction effect ($F_{(1,40)}=6.38$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.14$). Follow-up tests for the interaction effect conducted separately for the two autotelic NFT groups showed that for individuals low in NFT, negative emotional responses were not dependent on whether they were able to interact with an interface simulating stroking gestures, as the means did not differ significantly, see Figure 5 ($t_{(20)}=-0.16$, NS). However, as expected, participants high in autotelic NFT experienced far less negative emotions when using an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures ($M=0.18$), rather than using a static interface ($M=1.02$, $t_{(9)}=2.69$, $p<.05$, $r=.50$). These results confirm H4b.

Fig. 5. Interaction effect product presentation x autotelic NFT

DISCUSSION

Whether we touch to obtain information or to enjoy sensory feedback, touch plays a vital role in our decision-making process (Jansson-Boyd, 2011; Peck et al., 2013). Acknowledging

that actual touch is not always feasible, we built on research that has focused on tactile perceptual information provided through the sense of vision and extended it to the online shopping environment. With the help of Shooglet we designed an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures to provide consumers with tactile information in a mediated environment. Results reveal that such an interactive interface can in fact compensate for an inability to touch in a number of respects.

First, an interactive interface has shown to offer an informational function for experience attributes. An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures provides relevant product attribute information and is therefore perceived as highly diagnostic during product evaluation. In other words, the interactive cues seem to generate a vivid, informative, and impressive presentation of the product, and accordingly help consumers to intuitively gather information about texture, softness, and temperature. In line with our expectations, we found that image interactivity simulating stroking gestures can have similar effects on perceived diagnosticity, such as actual touch. These findings point to the significance of (interactive) visual stimuli capable of guiding thinking about touch elements as a significant process in mediated product experiences.

Second, emotional responses are regarded as one of the factors that contribute to the general superiority of direct experience over mediated experiences (Millar & Millar, 1996). Accordingly, an important question is whether an interactive interface can elicit emotional responses in the same way as actual touch. As to positive emotions we found that an interface simulating stroking gestures using image interactivity can elicit more positive emotional responses than a static interface. Image interactivity seems to sufficiently elicit positive emotional responses in such a way that touching the actual product does not arouse more positive emotions. Furthermore, we found no support for autotelic NFT affecting positive emotional responses. That is to say, image interactivity has a positive effect on emotional responses regardless of consumers' autotelic NFT. These results indicate that, against expectations, also for less haptically motivated consumers, an interactive interface elicits more positive emotional responses than a static interface. This may indicate that a static interface does not satisfy the basic needs for autotelic haptic information, even for individuals low in NFT. On the other hand, this effect may also be partly due to the 'newness' of the technology. Image interactivity itself is not a novel technology but the way it is applied in our study might have surprised the participants, which may have translated into positive emotional responses.

For negative emotional responses we found that consumers experience undesirable and unfavorable emotional responses when the ability to handle a product or interact with an interface simulating stroking gestures was denied. This pattern is particularly true for consumers high in autotelic NFT. The significant interaction effect tells us that consumers high in autotelic NFT experience more negative emotions when they use a static interface than when they use an interactive inter-

face. An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures has thus proven to reduce negative feelings for consumers high in autotelic NFT because the interactive cues apparently emphasize hedonic tactile information. Consumers low in NFT, however, are less negatively affected by the lack of opportunity to use an interactive interface. The level of image interactivity did not significantly affect negative emotional responses for those who are low in autotelic NFT. From this we can conclude that the 'newness' of the technology most likely did not affect the results. The interactive interface is capable of inducing mediated touch sensations to some extent because in the context of this study it affected consumers high in NFT in particular. However, for consumers high in autotelic NFT the results underscore that an interactive interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures does mainly prevent them from experiencing negative emotions but does not particular excel in eliciting positive emotions any more than for consumers low in NFT.

Until now, it has been assumed that certain senses, such as touch, are extremely difficult to stimulate in mediated environments. Despite recent important technological advances, mediated touch sensations in an online store remain relatively unexplored. This study addresses the calls of Grohmann et al. (2007) and Jansson-Boyd (2011) to deepen our understanding of how to overcome the inherent inability to integrate tactile input into online shopping. The present study offers convincing arguments for the viability of image interactivity to tap into tactile perceptual information, hence, affecting consumer responses. In this way, the results provide promising evidence to support the growing field of sensory-based marketing communication and extend it to an online environment.

Limitations and future research

The present research is subject to several limitations that future researchers should consider. A main limitation lies in the fact that this study was restricted to a single product category (a scarf). As a result, the present findings may not be generalizable to other products. Future research, incorporating product type as a moderator, can shed light on boundary conditions in which mediated touch experiences are elicited and play a role in product evaluations. Furthermore, only female students participated in this study. Besides excluding gender-specific preference for the product, this choice was also based on the fact that women have proven to base their judgments more often on what they perceive sensorially than men (Schifferstein, 2006). Women attach a high importance to sensory modalities in product evaluations, while men are potentially less aware of their sensory processes, or find cognitive information (product packaging, advertising, recommendations of friends and family) more important. Therefore, women are particularly interesting in the context of this study because they have been thought to suffer the most when tactile information is lacking (Citrin et al., 2003). Future research should include men in the sample as well to examine if the results replicate well. As described earlier, in the context of this study we cannot fully exclude the effect of the 'newness' of the

technology. Familiarity with the interface may be considered as a control factor in further studies. Furthermore, we created an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures. Nonetheless, there are more common ways in which people handle fabric material (pinching, scrunching, rubbing, etc.). Future research could include an interactive interface simulating multiple gestures to test if it encourages users to behave in a manner even more similar to those observed in brick-and-mortar stores. We also acknowledge that only one sensory modality was explored, other sensory modalities could be of importance as well. Sound in particular has proven to be strongly related to tactile experience and can potentially excel effects of an interactive interface when combined.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors of the study would like to thank SusaGroup for providing the online environment for the use of PrEmo.